

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

NOVEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Volume I Issue VII

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VII (November 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

EMMYLOU M. MANLANGIT, PhD

Associate Professor II/QMS-Unit Head

Bohol Island State University Candijay Campus

Bohol, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17505251](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17505251)

Making Calculus Easier Through an Interactive Learning App

Calculus is one of the core subjects offered to Computer Science students. It plays a vital role in the curriculum because it develops students' problem-solving and analytical skills, which are essential competencies in the field of computing. Moreover, proficiency in Calculus serves as a foundation for higher-level programming, algorithm analysis, and data modeling. The subject equips students with the ability to understand change, determine maximum and minimum values, and compute areas under curves. These skills are fundamental in modeling real-world phenomena and solving complex computational problems.

Despite its importance, many students continue to find Calculus challenging. This has been one of the persistent difficulties I have encountered in teaching the subject. When introducing derivatives and their basic rules, students often struggle to differentiate functions, resulting in low proficiency levels. Based on my observations, many students lack the necessary foundation in algebra, particularly in the laws of exponents and the manipulation of polynomial expressions. This gap becomes evident during class activities, where only a few can confidently solve problems on the board. Their quiz and exercise results also reflect these weaknesses, suggesting that difficulties in algebra directly affect their performance in Calculus.

To address this recurring issue, I initiated the development of an interactive learning application designed to make Calculus learning more engaging and accessible. I encouraged students with strong programming backgrounds to take the lead in designing and developing the app, organizing them into collaborative groups with specific roles and tasks. The interactive app focuses on strengthening learners' understanding of both algebraic and calculus concepts, emphasizing the laws of exponents, polynomial operations, and basic differentiation rules. While many similar platforms exist online, I wanted my students to create their own. Learning becomes more meaningful when students are actively involved in discovering, designing, and developing tools that enhance their understanding of the material. The app features concise lessons, step-by-step examples, and interactive exercises that promote mastery through practice and immediate feedback.

Currently, five student groups, each with a designated leader, have designed prototype applications. They have been encouraged to test their apps, gather feedback, and refine their designs. I continue to provide guidance and suggestions for improvement, which the groups integrate into their revisions. To evaluate the

Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VII (November 2025), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

app's usability and effectiveness, my co-teacher and I, in collaboration with an IT expert, have proposed a study examining its impact on students' engagement, attitudes, and proficiency in Calculus. The study will employ a pretest-posttest experimental design to measure learning gains, while usability testing will ensure the app's functionality, user friendliness, and educational value.

Through this initiative, I aim to promote innovation-driven, student-centered learning in mathematics education. By combining technology with collaboration, students not only strengthen their conceptual understanding but also develop essential skills in problem solving, creativity, and teamwork. Ultimately, this project aspires to make Calculus not only easier to learn but also more meaningful, interactive, and enjoyable for every learner.